

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-02

Nature-based sludge-drying reed bed for circular wastewater and biowaste management

//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Nature-based wastewater and sludge treatment

INPUTS

Sewage sludge from domestic wastewater

OUTPUTS

Stabilized nutrient-rich organic matter for agricultural purpose

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 8

CONTEXT & SCALE

Typically applied for the treatment and drying of sewage sludge generated from municipal wastewater treatment plants, particularly from small to medium-sized systems (reuse at household- up to farm-level)

KEY BENEFITS

Organic matter and Nutrient recovery;
Reduced fertilizer demand; Improved soil fertility and drought resilience.

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Access to suitable sewage sludge; structural support; regulatory compliance; monitoring; proper management;

CATEGORY

Wastewater & Biowaste Recycling

//02. WHAT IT IS

This solution offers an option for decentralized, nature-based sludge stabilization, enabling safe household and farm-level reuse of nutrients in farming systems. It combines low-tech sludge dehydration, mineralisation and stabilisation in a vegetated basin based on physical and biological processes.

Water content loss occurs due to gravity drainage through the filter layer and

evapotranspiration. Reed plants and drainage pipes also introduce oxygen to the sludge zone, allowing aerobic decomposition, mineralization, and stabilization of deposited sludge. The final product is humus-like material that can be used as a soil amendment in agriculture or landscaping, following verification of sludge quality through laboratory analysis, and in accordance with applicable regulatory requirements.

//03. WHY IT MATTERS

Sewage sludge contains valuable resources like phosphorus, carbon, and trace elements. At many municipal wastewater treatment plants, sludge is commonly managed through incineration, particularly where co-treatment of domestic and industrial wastewater limits reuse options. As a result, nutrients are largely lost, as the ash is typically disposed of in landfills.

The sludge-drying reed bed is a simple and effective nature-based solution for the local stabilization of sewage sludge.

The system operates with low maintenance requirements and does not rely on continuous machinery, energy, or fuel inputs, beyond periodic pumping. The stabilised, humus-like material can be further composted and returned to agricultural soils, contributing to increased soil organic matter, improved soil fertility and reduced reliance on mineral fertilizers. These effects support biomass production and crop yields and help strengthen farm resilience under increasing climate stress.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

Sludge Drying Reed Beds (SDRBs) can be adapted to various scales and climatic conditions. Key design parameters, including system size, depend on sludge characteristics and site-specific climate, with required areas typically ranging from 0.25–0.7 m² per population equivalent (PE). SDRBs consist of a watertight base layer (concrete or geomembrane) overlain by a filter layer composed of graded sand and gravel. Sludge is intermittently applied to the filter surface with loading cycles designed to ensure sufficient resting periods between applications to allow effective sludge dewatering.

During loading, solids are retained on the filter surface, while the percolating liquid is drained and returned to the wastewater treatment plant or on-site primary treatment unit. The filter layer is planted with macrophytes, typically *Phragmites australis*, whose root systems penetrate the accumulating sludge over the years, promoting sludge dewatering and stabilisation. The overall depth of the SDRB determines the operational lifespan of the bed and the interval before sludge removal is required.

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//05. HOW IT WORKS

In this solution sludge from a pre-treatment unit (e.g.: four-chamber septic tank) is intermittently loaded into a vegetated basin (Sludge-Drying-Reed-Bed), where it gets dewatered, stabilised, and mineralised through a combination of drainage, evapotranspiration, and biologically mediated processes. Loading is typically carried out with pumps or slurry tankers.. Sludge dewatering occurs through gravity drainage and evapotranspiration, while organic

matter is reduced through aerobic mineralization and biological stabilization. Reed plant root systems penetrate the sludge layer, enhancing oxygen transfer, improving drainage pathways, and stimulating microbial activity. Compared to conventional unplanted drying beds, nature-based SDRBs enable more effective sludge stabilization through combined physical and biological processes.

Schematic illustration of a Sludge Drying Reed bed © Tilley et al. 2014

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

Operations and maintenance are based on simple, routine procedures. Regular visual inspections are carried out to assess general system conditions, including hydraulics, odour development, potential leakages, and plant health. Sludge is intermittently loaded into the reed bed several times per year (e.g. four loading events), typically using an electric pump or slurry tanker, depending on site configuration.

SDRBs are designed for long-term sludge accumulation, with a typical operational

cycle of approximately five years. Prior to sludge removal, a prolonged resting period of at least six months is required to allow final stabilisation and die-off of potentially harmful pathogens. Before reuse, sludge samples should be analysed, and the final application must comply with local regulatory requirements. Following the operational cycle and sludge removal, the bed can be re-established and returned to service for a new loading period.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Health, environmental and technical risks, such as exposure to pathogens, blockages, accumulation of pollutants or anaerobic conditions, are effectively mitigated

through appropriate system design, regular operation and maintenance. The bed is fenced off so that unauthorized persons have no access.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

Farms operating at different scales, including market gardens and urban and peri-urban farms, with access to sewage sludge from domestic sources, and seeking decentralised nutrient recycling. Final reuse

depends on local regulations and the quality of the stabilised sewage sludge. Within the GEORGIA project this solution is implemented in [the pilot at the CAMBIUM ecovillage in southeastern Austria](#).

//09. KEYWORDS

Sludge Drying Reed Bed; Nature-based Solution; Decentralized; Nutrient recovery

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

//10. REFERENCES

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2. R. Bresciani and F. Masi "Sludge Drying Reed Bed – Technical Note for Urbanized Areas in India." Project report of NaWaTech project. N.A.
Online at: <https://sswm.info/sites/default/files/nawatech/Sludge%20Drying%20Beds%20-FINAL.pdf>
3. E. Tilley, L. Ulrich, C. Lüthi, P. Reymond and C. Zurbrügg "Compendium of sanitation systems and technologies". Second Edition. Swiss Federal Institute for Environmental Science and Technology (EAWAG), Duebendorf, Switzerland. 2014. Online at: https://www.eawag.ch/fileadmin/Domain1/Abteilungen/sandec/schwerpunkte/sesp/CLUES/Compendium_2nd_pdfs/Compendium_2nd_Ed_Lowres_1p.pdf https://www.eawag.ch/fileadmin/Domain1/Abteilungen/sandec/schwerpunkte/sesp/CLUES/Compendium_2nd_pdfs/Compendium_2nd_Ed_Lowres_1p.pdf

//11. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

1. Sustainable Sanitation and Watermanagement Toolbox:
<https://sswm.info/pavitr-toolkit/get-know-pavitr-technologies/water-reclamation-solutions/sludge-drying-reed-beds-for-faecal-sludge-treatment>
2. Nielsen S. "Sludge treatment and drying reed bed systems" *Ecohydrology & Hydrobiology*. Vol. 7, 3–4, p. 223–234. 2007.
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